

Teaching Portfolio

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Submission date: 31st January 2022

Declaration of independence

Declaration of independence for the teaching portfolio on OLAT

Author's name and first name:

Maria Alejandra Parreño
.....

Date of submission:

31st January 2022
.....

I hereby declare that I have written this work independently and only with the help of the sources mentioned in the directories or in the notes. I also certify that I have not used this work for other assessment purposes. I agree that the work may be checked for plagiarism with the appropriate software. **For this purpose, the University of Zurich reserves the right to commission suitable service providers in Switzerland and abroad. The UZH controls the data security guarantee of these service providers.**

First name, last name

Maria Alejandra Parreño
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Date

31st January 2022
.....

Signature

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1. Teaching philosophy

1.1. How do I teach?

I believe the best way to describe my teaching approach in higher education is that I teach with knowledge and with passion for knowledge, for learners that share this passion. The priority for me is to help the student identify the topics that they care about the most, validate their interest and provide a starting point for them to have the tools to continue exploring by themselves after the lesson/class is over. There are naturally specific goals and aims in accordance with a curriculum that fit in an educational context (e.g., in relation with subjects that came before) and that can be evaluated quantitatively for practical purposes of the students obtaining their final grades. However, the focus of the teaching and the approach is always placed in a bigger context, with as much individualized assistance to the learner as possible within the larger group.

1.2. Why do I teach in this way? What are my personal quality criteria?

Teaching in this way is in accordance to my values and gives purpose to my effort. Natural science is always evolving; new tools, data, ideas and questions arise continuously and every scientist knows that not one person will be able to possess all knowledge or “truths” to reveal to the student. I do not aim to provide knowledge per se, but to provide tools that help the student produce more knowledge, that at the same times makes them happy (as in “satisfies their curiosity and helps them achieve their goals). Higher education students have chosen a path based on their interest and more often than not there are one or more topics that set the spark that put them on this career path. For example, my spark has been my love for insects and how they interact with the rest of the organisms and the environment, something that I find fascinating. Some students in my classes find the relation between people and land

use interesting and relevant to study in the current socio-economic scenario they face. Others are attracted to the idea of manipulating nature for improving people's well-being. Yet others are driven by the idea of isolating yourself during field trips as a marine biologist or primate biologist, and being one with nature. I place my classes in bigger socio-ecological-economical contexts so students can explore what drives them in the career path, and what they can do with the skills they develop in it, for their own happiness and for science's sake.

My main personal quality criteria as a teacher are: Motivation, Research-based learning and Competence-oriented teaching, as discussed further in the reflection.

1.3. What, in my opinion, is student learning at university?

In my opinion student learning at university level is a period of time in which the student finds their place in the world, meaning the way in which they want to contribute to society. In this time, they work towards developing the skills needed to be successful on what they want to achieve, through interactions with peers as well as more experienced people (i.e., teachers).

1.4. How can I, as an instructor, promote student learning?

As an instructor, I promote student learning by: 1) preparing myself, with topic specific knowledge available and didactic tools that allow me to convey that knowledge, 2) providing a context for that knowledge that is relevant for the student at a certain point in space and time in which they participate in the lesson and 3) designing the lesson so that the student is not always passively receiving knowledge but that they also put their own questions and ideas into the lesson for general discussion, with the hope of building competences that will serve them later for applying them in their own research or jobs.

1.5. What is typical for good teaching in my discipline?

Traditionally in the past in natural sciences such as biology, teaching was considered good when it contained great part of information from the literature, usually loaded into the student for memorization (e.g., taxonomy for species identification in the field). Currently this focus has shifted to training students in the use of software and tools that greatly aid in synthesizing and grasping the large amounts of data and information available (e.g., R statistical software, databases for identification through pictures or for genome notation).

In terms of the teacher-student relationship, the shift has also greatly moved away from authorities providing “untouchable” knowledge, to a more collaborative work approach in which students are encouraged to question constantly existing knowledge and paradigms. A great example of this being the so called “journal clubs” in which students gather together in groups or pairs to scrutinize recent publications, a widespread activity in biology and related disciplines, across subjects.

1.6. What is the connection between the way I teach and the content I teach?

The content I teach within ecology, namely biodiversity assessments and human-nature interactions through land use, is intrinsically a subject that raises passions and opinions, and it is not purely objective. Even when talking about data, there is an underlying position taken within a cultural context of human domination over nature, of socio-economic classes fighting for land, of prioritization of species (e.g., charismatic or functional to humans) and budget allocation for science and ideas in a global context. This content is connected to the way I teach because I call for reflection from each individual student on which position, they take and which is the purpose of their work, explicitly. In a second instance, I prompt discussion with peers so that this student whose position in the world view is now explicit receives feedback from

others students that may have different world views, based on their backgrounds and story. The hope is of enriching their ideas, so that there is growth during the learning period, not only in technical and practical skill development, but also in their personal path.

1.7. How do I imagine my role as an instructor?

I currently see myself as a more experienced student, who is responsible for guiding beginner students. This is because I see myself constantly learning, making mistakes and expanding my skill-set, but with a large amount of experience and knowledge that can be useful for others. My role is to guide in the understanding of this knowledge and the built up of new questions for research.

2. Main Part

2.1. Teaching biography

Short description of the **individual teaching biography** (teaching formats, target groups and contents).

The first memory I have of teaching in any way was during highschool (aged 15-18) when I regularly provided “extra” lessons for my peers on natural and exact sciences, as well as primary school students, as a part-time job. This side job as a nachhilfe/teacher continued in parallel to my academic studies for 6 years, adding also online lessons in specialized international platforms (e.g. Tutor.com), teaching primary to university entry level for students of all backgrounds and ages, way before online teaching was as popular as it is today (2004-2012). Although arguably the format, objectives and naturally the level of complexity of teaching primary, secondary and university entry level is different than that in higher education, I believe these experiences served as a foundation for the ones that came after in higher education.

Throughout my post-secondary teaching experience, I can distinguish two types of activities in which I was in the role of teacher/lecturer: 1) knowledge transfer from a specialized audience to a non-specialized, be it to academic students from other disciplines (interdisciplinary translation/exchange) or to the general public interested in university doings and 2) formal teaching of course specific subjects in higher education for bachelor, master and doctoral students, which is the focus of higher education.

Knowledge transfer, sometimes called science communication or outreach, although not considered within higher education teaching, cannot be omitted from my teaching portfolio. Outreach experiences have provided me with great opportunities to explore

my own teaching philosophy and approach, as well as help myself get rid of doubt and self-inhibitions through numerous interactions with people with diverse backgrounds (which is not uncommon based on the literature¹). In my teaching style for higher education, I see a lot of the characteristics that make good outreach successful, such as appealing to the sense of wonder and guiding the learner in self-discovery, rather than downloading huge amounts of information for them to process. My knowledge transfer activities include the design of the Irchel Nature Trail processing research produced at the university for education, two sessions in the Moodle course Biodiversity and Global Change (currently in Coursera), a regular participation in the Biodiversity Means Life project from Science Lab and workshop design for conferences.

As for formal education to bachelor, master and doctoral students, I have been an assistant teacher as regulated for my doctoral studies, for more than 130 hours in Genetics, Ecology and Animal Behavior among other courses (see attached full list of courses). As an assistant PhD student, I was not in charge of designing lessons, but I was helping students solve specific tasks within workshops, practical lessons or supervising them during exams. Further experience in designing those lessons for higher education came from after my PhD, during my current first postdoc, when I have been able to design my first lecture-workshop: "Land-sharing, Land-sparing", tailored for the PhD course "Controversies in Ecology", which I have been teaching for two years at the University of Zurich (included in the Artifacts of my portfolio). A further experience that I must mention contributes to my teaching style, is the supervision of master and PhD students in Ecology (4 direct co-supervisions with the correspondent professors).

2.2. Reflection

2.2.1. What is characteristic for my teaching?

I reflect on my teaching mainly based on three quality criteria:

a) **Motivation**

b) **Research-based learning**

c) **Competence-oriented teaching**

a) Performance is highly related to motivation in higher education². This applies both to the teaching staff and the students. I remember going great lengths of effort when studying because I felt motivated to the subjects and to what I could do with them, and it is that same motivation that I need to be present in order to teach a compelling and interesting lesson. Therefore, one of the pillars of my teaching is to appeal to the motivation of the students, which I learn from through individual interactions and by observing peer interactions. Hands on activities and “choose your own adventure” within a couple of options are important for me to get a grasp of what motivates the student and then make groups based on that so the students are motivated throughout the lesson.

b) Research based learning (RBL) is the practice of incorporating real research or experimental activities typical from thesis proving, during the learning period³. Higher education students are bachelor, master and doctoral students, which in natural sciences must always carry a research thesis (of varying lengths according to academic level). I find it really important that in most science related courses, there would be not just lectures but hands on activities related to the research being done in that area. This encourages questioning, development of hypothesis, problem-solving skills, communication and other skills needed to successfully carry a scientific method. Research based does not

always imply a lab or a greenhouse, it can be also encouraging students to do research in their own backyards, in a field trip or on the computer with the use of interactive software (e.g., INVEST, for land use budget allocation).

- c) Competence-oriented teaching (COT) is the counterpart of competence based learning, which is better to define first, given that this teaching approach is centered on the student and not the professor⁴. It refers to the learning process being centered around the capacity and responsibility of each student to develop his autonomy in the learning process. In Competence based Learning (CBL) the curriculum is based on the understanding of which competences are necessary in today's world. Hence, competence-based teaching (CBT) is the approach that focuses on the students will to learn something, as a main aspect of the teaching/learning process. This concept is central to my approach when making a lesson, for example when preparing the ratio of lecture to interactive activities, I prioritize reduced groups of work focus on different aspects of the topic, rather than unified lectures that may not be of interest to everyone. I break down a major topic (e.g., land use impact on biodiversity) into different subtopics that can be discussed in reduced groups of the student's choice (e.g., agriculture, forestry, urbanization). Then I promote literature search within the group and discussions of specific examples, that can be then shared with the rest of the groups in the wrap up.

2.2.2. On which concepts do I base my teaching?

As mentioned in my biography, my very first experiences in teaching were in primary and highschool teaching, where my didactic approach was based on Piaget and Vygotsky theories of cognitive development and constructive learning⁵. The pivot concepts in summary would be that they identified that children and adults think in

a different way and that learning occurs through stages that built up on each other, with great influence from the socio-economic environment and an important role of tutors and guidance. In this matter, I have written a paper about how these concepts may be applied to understanding of biodiversity throughout life and how context and everyday life activities in childhood may be a source of misunderstandings later in life (including higher education). You can find this paper in the Artifacts of this portfolio.

Piaget and Vygotski's theories were developed for the study of learning in the initial levels and are usually still largely limited to these stages. Yet many of the ideas that are a backbone in cognitive development and constructive learning can also be seen in the light of higher education, with adaptations ^{6,7}. Two of those concepts that I would like to mention as they are part of my teaching approach, are the student's motivation to learn as an important feature of the learning process and critical thinking as an advanced conceptualization ⁸. The first one relates to the intrinsic motivation to learn, which is in children a "biologically defined" curiosity to understand new situations that are in dissonance with what is known until that point in time⁹. In higher education, motivation is arguably still the main force behind trying to understand the world around us, and is the main reason why a young adult or adult student freely chooses a career and sticks through it. The second one, critical thinking, is referred to in Piaget's Formal Operational Reasoning stage, that when present, is achieved by the student in adolescence/adulthood. However, research indicates that most of the population is not arriving to adulthood with fully developed operational thinking skills, among which is critical thinking ¹⁰. University is for most people a period of time in which students get challenged a higher levels, prompting the development of formal operational skills, such as hypothesis testing and critical thinking. I have this very present when developing my lessons, that I should challenge the student enough in this respect.

More specifically developed for higher education, is the concept of Metacognition, or “thinking about thinking”, which I also use in my lessons¹¹. Metacognition promotes critical and creative thinking of the individual by encouraging problem-solving through multiple solutions and information integration, rather than isolation through specific disciplines structure. “Thinking about thinking” refers to the capacity of the student to elaborate their own self-assessment¹², so that with practice and coaching, they eventually become independent in learning – a goal that I find tightly linked with the goal of becoming an independent researcher in academia.

2.2.3. What challenges do I face in teaching? How do I deal with these challenges?

Since my teaching is as individually oriented as possible so as to make profit from motivation and personal experiences, one of the challenges I face is to keep the classroom cohesive and peer-interaction meaningful. I deal with this by limiting somewhat the number of options available for choice during the activities. For example, in a journal club in a classroom of 12 students, I aim to have maximum 3 groups working on different papers of their liking, but not more to prevent students isolated. I also limit the number of option of papers to choose within those groups, to those papers from which conclusions can be exchanged in cohesion with the other groups, not only for exposition but to prompt questioning from other groups with slightly different topics. Measuring the learning outcomes is something that I need to take into account when designing the tasks to fit potential motivations in the students¹³.

In the same direction, in order to have a research-based teaching lesson, it is convenient for me to find groups of students with similar motivations that can work together harmonically and then exchange with others. In my lessons I have dealt with this challenge by pairing people up by country of origin, since the main computer lab task in my course is exploring the land use management per country in a comparative way. This has worked well overall, as students from or with interest in a particular

country seem to know much better than others how to interpret results and where to look for specific parameters with cultural influence. Still, when I reflect on this exercise I find that there is still some room for improvement, as I am unsure how this method serves different learning styles¹⁴. The concept of learning styles, though controversial in the literature, simplifies the idea that not every student is responding to stimuli in the same way (e.g., visual, auditive, convergent). Consistent with this, I find that some students respond to working with visual maps (part of this exercise on land use) exciting, while others lay back and let other members of the team take the reins. This could be due to group dynamics or due to different learning styles in the group, and is something that I would be willing to look more into in the next editions of the workshop.

On the other hand, the challenges I face with competence-oriented teaching are mostly related to the risk of oversimplifying a research topic or reducing the scope of it to technical or practical aspects, reducing its potential to be seen as a valid basic or “academic” research. Another difficulty is that I often lack specifics on what previous competences the students have, given that my courses are usually undertaken by students from different disciplines and academic and social backgrounds. I overcome this by making a glossary in my slides and doing series of short paired activities in which I can assess the student’s current standing. But in the future, I will be incorporating an initial assessment through a questionnaire sent previous to the course, as I learnt at the Teaching Skills course.

2.3. Future options for action

Through the Teaching Skills course as well as the didactica courses (in particular the 1 year Teaching Sciences at University) I have learnt a myriad of new techniques that I would like to apply to my teaching approach and lesson design. In particular, I believe that I can get better at choosing more effective and suitable teaching strategies

if I can read better the students learning styles and their pre-existing knowledge. This will be the focus of improvement for myself in the next editions of the course. While I believe that I have mastered the appeal for motivation in students and encourage their critical thinking, I still think I can improve in the use of models and analogies to structure my teaching so that it is easier for them to follow.

2.4. Conclusion

Overall, my goal is to inspire students and I strive to create a space for them to show their own motivations and find their place in the scientific and social community. Although I do not have yet vast experience in higher education, this portfolio shows my interest for improving the way I convey my science through teaching, with the idea of including all students in the process of learning, at their own pace and with their individual goals present. I strive to expand my theoretical knowledge and look for new ways to apply it in the classroom. No doubt this is work in progress and with further experience and evaluations, I shall evolve this portfolio in the near future.

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3. Artefacts

3.1. Teaching reflection on Analogies to teach “hard topics”

TOOLS FOR TEACHING “HARD” TOPICS

What is a “hard” topic to teach?

- ▶ Rather abstract
- ▶ Numerical; computational
- ▶ Higher order thinking, rather than memorization
- ▶ Complex systems

What are some tools to guide student’s learning?

- ▶ Analogies
-

a is to b like c is to d

bird is to nest like bee is to beehive

- ▶ As a learning tool (to understand how systems work)
- ▶ As a learning outcome (to learn to extrapolate mechanisms learnt and use them across systems)

Richland, L.E. & Simms, N., (2015), Analogy, higher order thinking, and education, WIREs Cogn Sci, doi: 10.1002/wcs.1336

E.G. META-ANALYSIS

Definition: a set of statistical methods and techniques for aggregating, summarizing, and drawing inferences from collections of related studies

- **Analogy 1:** "Its like comparing pears and apples" - used as a critique. But could also be used as a learning analogy, when explained further.
- **Drawback:** phrase with a negative connotation

E.G. META-ANALYSIS

Definition: a set of statistical methods and techniques for aggregating, summarizing, and drawing inferences from collections of related studies

- **Analogy 2:** "If you make a food recipe many times and it always gives similar but different results. Sometimes its more salty, sometimes its more acid, sometimes its more burnt, etc. What would you do to find out the reason?" You would check at the number of ingredients and their brands, you could check the number of steps you followed each time, you could verify if you always used the same kitchen equipment... A study is like a cooking recipe. And a meta-analysis is looking at all the aspects of cooking a recipe to find why its always giving a different results every time you do it.
- **Benefits:** replication of recipe is like study sources, there are multiple variables that can be modified and alter the result.
- **Drawback:** recipes are meant to give similar results probably less heterogeneous that what you find in nature.

Effect - Outcome
cooking a recipe - dish

Multiple studies
repeating the same recipe

Modifiers
number of ingredients
brand of ingredients
elements used
ambient temperature

REMARKS

- Analogies have been proven to be good tools in teaching
- This is specially the case in difficult topics
- Its not always easy to find a good analogy that will work for everyone
- Daily life activities and experiences could make good examples

THANK YOU

3.2. Controversies in Ecology course – Land use/Land sparing lesson

Alejandra Porraño

This morning

- Introduce the terms land sparing and land sharing
- History of the debate
- Name main arguments on each side
- New directions
- Practical exercise on developing counter-arguments
- Read and debate 2 specific conflicts

We want it all

Existing land use strategies

- Examples:
- Pristine national parks
 - High input farming
 - Dense and compact cities

RSPB Centre for Conservation Science

Existing land use strategies

RSPB Center for Conservation Science

At a landscape scale

- Minimizes land demand for farmland
- Increases yield
- Boosts wild population on farmland
- Decreases yield

Fischer et al. 2008 Should agricultural policies encourage land sparing or wildlife-friendly farming?

At a landscape scale

Fischer et al. 2008 Should agricultural policies encourage land sparing or wildlife-friendly farming?

Equilibrium theory of island biogeography (revisited)

MacArthur and Wilson, 1967

Equilibrium theory of island biogeography (revisited)

Applied to landscapes

- Landscape fragments are like islands
- Surrounding habitats are hostile
- Natural pre-fragmentation was uniform

Halls 2002, A conceptual genealogy of fragmentation (...)

Main controversy

What is the best strategy to preserve biodiversity with the least lost in yields?

Green et al 2005 Farming and the fate of wild nature

- Agriculture and farming: main threat to biodiversity
- Land sharing schemes: costly, 2.7 billion euros in farmer subsidies to compensate for lost yield
- If yield in land sharing schemes is too low, the benefits are reduced because too much land is required
- Land sparing supports larger populations of species (i.e. birds)

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Norman Borlaug
Agronomist, Nobel Peace Prize

14

Main controversy

What is the best strategy to preserve biodiversity with the least lost in yields?

Norman Borlaug
Agronomist, Nobel Peace Prize

What do you think?

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Criticisms to the Borlaug hypothesis (and Land sparing)

High input / intensity agriculture is highly damaging and unsustainable

Reap profit for big companies (not compatible with small subsistence farming or cultural practices)

Not realistic: more food, cheaper, and land still is used up

Not practical: there is just not enough land to do it anymore

- 85% terrestrial surface is outside reserves and is in use (Western and Peart, 1990)
- 70% of the land in the tropics is in mixed landscapes already

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Is land sharing good enough to support biodiversity?

Population size: Mostly not

Most studies found species have larger populations when food is produced in the smallest area possible (support land sparing) (Helen et al 2011, Egan and Mortensen 2012)

17

Is land sharing good enough to support biodiversity?

Species richness: Highly dependant

Specific species, on the ecosystem, on the scale, on the type of activity

18

Is land sharing good enough to support biodiversity?

What we know

- Suitable for species that require low intensity agriculture
- Landscapes with complex topography (no machines), gradients of productivity, with poor or degraded soils
- Communities with high species turnover
- Land history and multiple ownerships leads to heterogeneity in usage

Best assets

- Landscape continuity may assist in increasing resilience to climate change
- "Externalities" from agricultural productivity are lower (or technically they don't exist)

Fischer et al. 2008 Should agricultural policies encourage land sparing or wildlife friendly farming?

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Main controversy

What is the best strategy to preserve biodiversity with the least lost in yields?

Ideas

- low intensity agriculture > low yield
- Is yield the most important? Profitability?
- Intermediate levels of disturbance support high levels of biodiversity
- Holistic land use planning includes a variety of land uses and not just extremes

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Main controversy

What is the best strategy to preserve biodiversity with the least lost in yields?

What Have We Learned from the Land Sparing-sharing Model?

by C. Donaldson, C. Ferraz

Department of Forest Ecosystems and Society, College of Forestry, Oregon State University, Corvallis, OR 97331, USA

Programa de Pós-graduação em Ecologia e Biomecânica, Instituto de Biologia, Universidade Federal de Bahia, Salvador, Bahia 41310-110, Brazil

Received: 20th April 2018; Accepted: 24 May 2018; Published: 28 May 2018

Keywords: Land sparing, Land sharing, Agricultural intensification, Biodiversity, Land use change

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Half Earth Project

"I want us to create a system of natural reserves or specially managed areas large enough to save—indeinitely, in natural conditions—a very large percentage of the species on earth," Wilson (Esri UC Plenary Session)

Half-Earth - Edward O. Wilson

€11.99

bucher.de

Free shipping

By Goodie

22

Half Earth Project

MacArthur and Wilson, 1967, The Theory of Island Biogeography

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Half Earth Project

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3.3. Script for the MOOC Biodiversity and Global Change: Science and Action for UZH, now in Coursera
<https://www.mooc.uzh.ch/en/courses/archive/biodiversity.html>

Persons in this video: [Alejandra](#)

Location: UZH

Date & time to be filmed: July 12th morning

Resources used:

.....

Supplementary material mentioned in this video:

sli de	Audio (black font means that voice is coming from the off, i.e. person not visible)	Visuals: Text (black font) or image or video (description in grey font)	Remarks (e.g. copyright, status) (in grey font)
1.	Music?	UZH logo: University of Zurich	–
2.	Music?	Biodiversity and Global Change: Science & Action	–
3.	Music?	Biodiversity and Global Change: Science & Action Module 6: Conservation, policy, politics and action	–
4.	Music?	Biodiversity and Global Change: Science & Action Lesson 2: Biodiversity, politics and business.	–
5.	Music?	Biodiversity and Global Change: Science & Action Video 1: Biodiversity organizations, policies and treaties.	–
6.	Hi, my name is Alejandra Parreño and I am a PhD student at the University of Zurich. For my thesis, I look at the effects that the actions of humans have on the biodiversity on Earth.	María Alejandra Parreño	–
7.	In this video I will talk about international policy regarding the protection of biodiversity. First we will have a look at why it is important to take policy into account when talking	Content of video <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intro to lesson • Actors in policy making • Intergovernmental organizations meetings: the Rio Summit 1992, • What is a convention? Biodiversity-related conventions 	

	<p>about biodiversity. Then I will mention the different actors in policy making and their roles, to then focus more on the intergovernmental organizations. In this context, we will look at what happens when these organizations meet and the major breakthroughs in international policy making.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brief history of the Convention of Biological Diversity (CBD). • Concrete outcomes of the CBD. 	
8.	<p>[Ale’s voice] Global challenges like the loss of biodiversity are difficult to address for many reasons. One of them is that they are caused by activities that involve multiple groups of interest (called stakeholders). Another reason is that they cross boundaries of countries and cultures. This means that in order to tackle them, agreements, measures and controls at different levels must be decided in cooperation.</p>	<p>Financing Climate Change picture</p> <p>Palm oil production picture</p> <p>Orangutan picture</p>	<p>Credit: ItzaFineDay, Flickr.com</p> <p>Retrieved from https://www.flickr.com/photos/itzafineday/3085307050/in/photolist-5GD19-4chkWQ-dNwK8K-5p59sA-oERpnX-fh6FTU-5GyRZc-5vWHf5-dQvZtC-jq8ouH-74oqeE-eGKYh6-9mkSU-fgRkXv-7kXBvy-4dn7uw-eGL8iH-745Zz8-q6m6EH-fgRoUr-BCNFEC-eGScmE-4dia18-fh6y9q-fgRe9D-fh6KoL-fh6GKY-paP1hE-92QnBj-fh6Hgb-HTXVhG-HTa5T5-fh6snA-6QtpAN-eG56tq-914qdE-JMclUy-fh6xr9-fh6rTU-fh6w2C-Ju3J31-Jof6rq-JxXU36-fh6uZ1-fh6wVJ-eL6ZuM-fh6wuL-nxRuYc-fgRdCT-fh6vBb</p> <p>Credit: Benketaro, Flickr.com</p> <p>retrieved from https://www.flickr.com/photos/misskei/5614842815/in/photolist-9yax9K-zrxXC-4AYCVn-4B3Veu-bmC84g-47tJUN-bJvDDH-4B3Twm-rF15z4-bpLkZD-ehxfcf-aYBcua-4AYEpr-hW4gbi-pt3qH-jexq6M-hVZw15-hVYYTM-hW4wPU-pEdNJY-c44mVw-hW4QCE-6azHgC-hVZBfo-hVZ5B-hW4cQG-hW4FFw-bpLm72-hW58vK-hW4tPz-7kpTRx-4QwFSU-hW4BiH-hVY3r8-7kpTEX-hVWiCq-hVZyHm-hW2Khk-hVZbTu-hW4aeh-rerR7L-it8sZf-it3mh7-9C8BYq-hW4Hh5-bpLmde-niqPcn-bmC7Pz-6FpVva-665QmZ</p> <p>credit: Marta Diarra, Flickr.com,</p> <p>retrived from: https://www.flickr.com/photos/119670994@N05/13008997424/in/photolist-kPyvH3-8zNsm4-eXUyrJ-5wTyqV-q2DeEZ-9FbCHp-9bydet-5wTxMn-oXZ4q7-bBTGw6-cQZhx7-aPzwG-LPrsA-eCFxaH-eajQX8-8zNuPz-6dE2E-9DJV9Z-hmsCsk-HtBqs-nfipJZ-8zRAJC-75BErW-9JdFJx-EevHq-FLpHT-8zRAF7-5Dhhqr-EevYN-5DUa1o-fhkru-6HC9Ka-Eevqd-EevP9-75BEdG-6qaXR4-o635Wa-FLpHi-3Ffwz-zuNZ2-Eexec-cpjMyJ-4E9pK-56Qz2q-g1QcCN-2S9T3-56LGgn-4gnDRL-56QzY7-56Lrsp</p>
9.	<p>[Ale’s voice] So, what is the role of policy makers and politicians? They are responsible for elaborating plans and making decisions regarding what actions to take and when, what budget there is available for this, who should be carrying</p>	<p>Man in the microphone picture</p>	<p>Credit: United States Mission Geneva, Flickr.com</p> <p>Retrieved from: https://www.flickr.com/photos/us-mission/11984049484/in/photolist-jfZooQ-dEbUvT-8ZsL8k-jcXTYU-bW5juS-75mmvs-9Evrmd-rXqAwp-3MLJV8-bW5kas-rZbpHE-bW5kPN-dhkBSP-6a8z9m-3hDuH6-rZan6f-bW5kZC-8pfFrJ-75mmHw-rZirEv-oY8c4x-8ZsBLE-os3obG-n4vr7H-mUUW8P-c657pQ-9C4nwz-9ueHKM-8ZsKtD-3VB3Hh-75mmUE-sesBzA-3VB3k9-sgAN5G-bW5jRE-sesB3U-sgAMrs-7Fhpgh-jcVFge-8pfFAq-c5rznL-bW5kRs-nhAwt-9C7gcY-jcZY5C-9Ad4DL-8pcvqv-3VAPJ-9C6ZVG-48dt5Y</p>

	the plans out and also to record what has been done so far and learn from mistakes.		
10.	There are several actors in policy making: governments, intergovernmental organizations, NGOs, and the public.	Actors in policy making: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Governments - Intergovernmental organizations - Non-governmental organizations - The public 	
11.	Governments are responsible for implementing measures at a national level and deciding the budget that will be allocated for it.	Actors in policy making: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Governments - Intergovernmental organizations - Non-governmental organizations - The public 	
12.	Intergovernmental organizations are made up of representatives from several countries and provide a space to catalyze cooperation, decide responsibilities and set an international agenda. Examples are the United Nations and the IUCN.	Actors in policy making: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Governments - Intergovernmental organizations - Non-governmental organizations - The public 	
13.	NGOs are independent from states and not for profit. They respond to a particular interest but have no responsibility in terms of outcomes. Examples of international NGOs are the World Wildlife Fund, The Nature Conservancy and Greenpeace. Examples of national NGOs are The National Wildlife Federation in	Actors in policy making: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Governments - Intergovernmental organizations - Non-governmental organizations - The public 	

	<p>the United States, The Friends of the Earth in Germany, ProNatura in Switzerland, the Australian Conservation Foundation in Australia and the Fundación Vida Silvestre in Argentina.</p>		
14.	<p>The fourth actor in policy making is the public, that is the whole society, because everyone has an influence on the other actors, whether it is as support or control. Ultimately, every person has to live with the consequences of the results of agreements. That is why it is crucial that society gets involved in the decision making process.</p>	<p>Actors in policy making:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Governments - Intergovernmental organizations - Non-governmental organizations - The public 	
15.	<p>[Ale's voice] In this video, the focus is on intergovernmental organizations, so you can learn more about their role.</p> <p>The way international organizations interact is by getting together to discuss issues and to put together the outcomes in documents. The meeting and the outcomes are both called „conventions“.</p>	<p>United Nations headquarters</p>	<p>Credit: Hibino, Flickr.com</p> <p>retrieved from: https://www.flickr.com/photos/hibino/51544012/in/photolist-5ybeS-e2wZpQ-qpHUkB-aVC7jk-cH4bRG-9Ng7P2-e2rmJP-ayzmrF-Gwpko-7x5Fmz-5ybfv-cdfoaA-ag7qxvF-bVT9A6-8XHDcZ-9yZ78z-92gnMT-ayC3QE-ayC15E-EpZaf-9LpVBR-5ybdS-ujKMzd-9ZN8u2-GwpCd-8z5Zjj-cdfqU-GwtML-cEb1wh-bVT84z-aTW8Ve-hiko11-aEPunQ-2pQiz8-pXW9sB-2pUC1h-e3W31o-e4ZyeB-8ngDsr-cdfqXm-9LpPNR-djtSxj-bWgTey-eW1nG-8vBVTe-8vEXjo-cdfqA1-7PePDH-c9rnA7-8vtyRx</p>
16.	<p>In international policy making, we find seven biodiversity related conventions: on plant protection, on wetlands, on</p>	<p>Biodiversity related conventions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - plant protection - wetlands - world heritage and 	

	<p>world heritage and cultural services, on migratory species, on the trade of endangered species, on genetic resources for food and on biological diversity in general.</p>	<p>cultural services</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- migratory species- trade of endangered species- genetic resources for food- biological diversity	
17.	<p>So, how does a convention come to life? A first draft of a convention is written by working groups, usually belonging to different specialized sections of the United Nations, called Programmes (for example, the Environmental Programme). Then, it is opened for modifications and signatures of countries that agree with its content. "Party members" are countries that agreed with the latest text of a whole convention. They send delegations to regular meetings, in order to discuss the challenges faced and the shared responsibilities. Some countries might not sign the whole convention but agree with part of it.</p>	<p>No image</p>	
18.	<p>The first major breakthrough in international agreements on climate change and the protection of biodiversity came at the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development in Rio de Janeiro in June 1992. This conference is commonly called The Earth Summit or Rio Summit.</p>	<p>The Earth Summit (1992)</p>	

19.	<p>Three important conventions were opened for signature at the Earth Summit:</p> <p>The United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, that later developed the Kyoto Protocol.</p> <p>The United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification</p> <p>and the United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), which represents a major breakthrough for sustainable development.</p> <p>These three are also referred to as „The Rio Conventions“</p>	<p>The Earth Summit (1992):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Convention on Climate Change (Kyoto Protocol) - Convention to Combat Desertification - Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) 	
20.	<p>[Ale’s voice] Through the CBD, the party members recognized biodiversity as a common concern for humanity and agreed to implement national programmes for:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) conservation of biodiversity, 2) promotion of sustainable use of its components and 3) fair and equitable sharing of benefits from resources globally. 	<p>Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conservation of biodiversity - Promotion of sustainable use - Sharing of benefits from resources (hands with the world drawn picture) <p>Picture: party members of the CBD</p>	<p>Credit: Wikipedia, retrieved from https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Convention_sur_la_diversit%C3%A9_biologicalue#/media/File:Convention_on_Biological_Diversity2.svg</p> <p>Sharing of benefits picture credit: Sasha Peterson, Flickr.com</p> <p>Retrieved from:</p>
21.	<p>Conventions are good for expressing shared interests and for providing guidelines for working in cooperation.</p>	<p>Intergovernmental Panel of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES)</p>	

	<p>The countries that signed the Biodiversity Convention frequently meet to discuss its implementation. At the 9th such meeting in 2008, it was decided to establish the Intergovernmental Panel of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services, short IPBES. This is a group of people that works to link the knowledge we have about biodiversity and ecosystem services around the world.</p>		
<p>22.</p>	<p>[Ale’s voice] Another important outcome of the convention is the Nagoya protocol. In this case, protocol means an agreement on several obligations when using a resource. The Nagoya protocol is a legal document that deals with obligations for people using genetic resources. Genetic resources are the genetic material that is found in organisms, that may be of current or future use to humans. Countries have the right to use the species and the genetic resources they find in their territory. However, by signing the Nagoya Protocol, they agree to share the benefits of using them. These benefits can be knowledge and research on the resources, but also commercial use, like for example, agriculture and food.</p>	<p>Nagoya Protocol Picture: hands with several tomatoe varieties</p>	<p>Credit: Nick Harris, Flickr.com Retrieved from: https://www.flickr.com/photos/nickharris1/4883388027/in/photolist-dx779k-iNpH9k-8rwD8l-duxPam-8fDGhp-j2uXQf-dx76ga-9Vx3cB-duxP9L-duxPb3-dx77hD-dxcxCm-oZqR3e-oYSgnc-516ZBF-cRhAwd-ai6QoT-7YredL-bs8imm-9PaN4m-89QNoM-39CYpN-duxP9b-eNV7Qj-d3HMHu-dxcBUo-9Vx5oX-5pfbC-84aSPo-d3HMF1-5gwnRF-5oWZVA-8qZqGG-5gAGx5-duxPbS-5gwkNP-5gwovR-5e14K0-B7ezmC</p>
<p>23.</p>	<p>Also in Nagoya, countries adopted the „The strategic</p>	<p>Strategic Plan for Biodiversity 2010-2020</p>	

	<p>plan for biodiversity“ which includes the Aichi Biodiversity Targets for the period 2010-2020. This is a document that lists a number of goals to achieve in biodiversity management. Although: it doesn’t say how to do it! This has to be decided by each country itself.</p>	Aichi Biodiversity Targets	
24.	<p>Some examples of the targets are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - reduce the loss of natural habitats at least by half or bring close to zero, - protect a certain percentage of the land and water areas of each country, - restore 15% of degraded areas, - reduce pressure on coral reefs. 	<p>Some of the <u>Aichi Biodiversity Targets</u>:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - at least halve or bring close to 0 the loss of natural habitats, - protect a certain percentage of the areas of the country - restore 15% of degraded areas - reduce pressure on coral reefs. 	
25.	<p>So through this video, we have learned who are the actors involved in policy making related to biodiversity and the major current treaties. A take home message: we can only tackle global loss of biodiversity if we willingly sit down together to discuss and agree on why this is important and we set common goals. Policy making is a good way to democratically debate and take decisions. If you’d like to learn more about international environmental policy and the actions of international organizations, you can explore the links in</p>	Hands with the world picture	<p>https://www.flickr.com/photos/119744475@N05/13013527253/in/photolist-kPXJgx-5P5p5e-dtArqs-f34pBh-oq3scc-6ovb1p-2Ude9W-pSnPrH-kPXNUR-nTnUXG-f34opE-d9xBrU-5G7M1o-3gHzS2-e8uiXS-ps8ZxD-pQh86f-pSnNVx-6iim8k-q5FA1Y-d9xKqo-5XWh9h-6XmDET-oVwj3J-pzTabF-qoLnb1-pSnPhK-mUVCzu-7mxw8S-pzYEE1-6F9qc8-pzTa5Z-88nFCN-6MotkX-cXSQmb-oVzpZB-pSrY53-nnBU9c-pSnPoB-br1wNd-7qG1v4-8Pquy8-qQSAAV-p5JvNH-ydDPCQ-ojAfUB-c78zBj-doJeQb-7Et6fZ-fJRLKE</p>

	the supplementary document on the course website.		
26.		Instructors in this video: Alejandra Parreno University of Zurich, IEU and Dept. of Geography © University of Zurich, Institute for Evolutionary Biology and Environmental Science	

3.4. Paper on how children understand biodiversity, applying Piaget and Vygotski’s theories (available at <https://osf.io/preprints/socarxiv/bqvxp/>)

“How might everyday experiences shape biodiversity understanding? A perspective to spark new research”

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Abstract

In this perspective article we start from the theories of constructivism and conceptual change within the field of education to develop and present hypotheses about how understandings of biodiversity and diversity more generally are formed. We argue that extrinsic and circumstantial elements from everyday experiences are relevant in shaping understandings of biodiversity.

We discuss how children's games and food-related experiences may influence how children form conceptions of biodiversity. We focus on 'misconceptions,' areas where conceptions differ from established ideas in ecology. These include: underestimating the importance of diversity for "complementarity" and over-simplifications of how nature works. Firstly, we examine a type of children's game that often concerns biodiversity and consists of a puzzle where the forming of categories is encouraged. Secondly, we discuss people's relation to nature through food in their diets.

We believe that targeted intervention is needed to move towards an inclusive and multi-faceted representation of biodiversity, one that emphasises fundamental properties that make a whole and interacting parts. We argue that experiences of games and food can be pivotal in developing a deeper understanding of these fundamental properties of biodiversity. These would be important experiences to consider when attempting transformative change of relationships between people and nature.

Keywords: diversity, biodiversity attitudes, food experiences, children's games, environmental education

Introduction

We start from an understanding of biodiversity developed in the environmental sciences and adopted in national and international environmental policy. The UN Convention on Biological Diversity defines biodiversity as the variety and number of living organisms in the world or in a particular habitat, including humans (Convention on Biological Diversity, 2010; Magurran, 2004). We acknowledge that this definition only represents one of multiple perspectives on biodiversity (and therefore is limited in scope), likely biased by our upbringing as WEIRD (western, educated, industrialized, rich and democratic) authors (Heinrich, 2010). Biodiversity plays an important role in ecosystem functioning and adaptation to change (Cardinale et al., 2012; Duffy, 2009). Tackling the global biodiversity decline often requires the involvement of people in decision making that are not biodiversity scientists (Johnson et al., 2017, Michel & Backhaus 2019). The notions people have about biodiversity have been shown to affect their support of biodiversity management measures (Buijs, Fischer, Rink, & Young, 2008, Hooykaas et al., 2020). It is relevant to ask how the concept of biodiversity develops in lay people, a study that would be within the scope of environmental education (Kassas, 2002). Here we formulate the question as follows: how do every day experiences shape people's notions of biodiversity?

Throughout this paper we refer to “diversity” when we talk about a group of different elements that are not biological and to biodiversity when the group contains biological elements (usually organisms). Humans can perceive biodiversity using all their sensory organs, through aspects such as diversity of colours, shapes, sounds, and tastes. For early humans, experiencing biodiversity meant understanding, for example, which species they could eat and which were poisonous, or which could be used as medicine, a valuable asset for survival (Oksanen & Pietarinen, 2004). There is practical value in being able to derive information about biodiversity from everyday life experiences. In his works on ethnobiology, Berlin (1992) tells of the large and specific knowledge contained in traditional, non-literate societies of many parts of the world, on plant and animal classifications. Many of these systems of classification are comparable to or better in depth and accuracy than scientific taxonomy (Atran et al., 2002).

While some children grow up immersed in knowledge about plant and animal species, many learn about biodiversity from secondary sources, which could also lead to misconceptions. Since biodiversity is a term that was coined in the scientific realm, for the purpose of this perspective, we speak of “misconceptions” in cases of beliefs, views and opinions that are inconsistent with the science-based worldview underlying most national and international environmental policy documents. For us--authors with an academic background--narratives, stories and other lay people's accounts of biodiversity have an educational value to convey the scientific concept of biodiversity, as long as they are consistent with it. We do, however, acknowledge that in other contexts (e.g., religious rituals) different notions of biodiversity are very important and equally valid (and often the different notions are connected, see e.g. Frascaroli et al. 2014).

According to constructivist theories in education, misconceptions can emerge from everyday experiences and also from inaccurate, incomplete or incorrect teaching (Coley & Tanner, 2012). Such misconceptions can, for example, be based on the idea that correlation implies causation or the misunderstanding that humans evolved from monkeys. A common misconception regarding biodiversity is, for example, to think that people and other species should not or cannot coexist in urban spaces; that each needs their separated space to thrive. This misconception is particularly held by people that live in urban spaces and have only

learned about conservation projects as being valid and useful in pristine areas, such as national parks (Soanes et al., 2019). In education, misconceptions can be regarded as a normal part of the learning process; but they need to be identified and addressed in order to lead a learner through a conceptual change process towards a more accurate understanding (Moore et al., 1990).

Environmental cognition is concerned with the way we learn about the environment, including how small children understand the environment that surrounds them (Palmer et al., 1996). Numerous misconceptions in children about different aspects of biology have been identified but little attention has been given in particular to the concept of biodiversity (Coley & Tanner, 2012). Identifying misconceptions, their origin and their associations early is important to develop a more accurate and effective curriculum that gives the correct tools to people involved in education. In the absence of a conceptual change, some misconceptions may result in detrimental decisions. For example, misconceptions regarding how the immune system works are one of the cited causes for parents to not vaccinate their children against some diseases, increasing their own vulnerability and that of their community (McKee and Bohannon, 2016). We suggest that there is scope and need for research into whether misconceptions regarding biodiversity and its functional significance exist, how they are created, and how they may be appropriately addressed. More specifically, we develop and describe (but do not test here) the hypothesis that many experiences of daily life activities regarding a) children's games and b) food cooking and eating may be relevant to how people form notions around the concept of biodiversity.

The general aim of this article is to propose a perspective on how biodiversity understanding could be shaped by informal experience, to raise awareness of the current lack of research in this realm, and to present hypotheses that could promote dialogue and spark further research. We use two examples to illustrate our perspective: 1) children's games with representations of organisms and 2) contents of people's diets. In both examples, experiences can help or hinder people's understanding of how biodiversity matters for the maintenance of a healthy environment and can help people to reconnect with the biodiversity that is near them. All of our hypotheses are largely untested, and we do not here present tests of them. Furthermore, it is beyond the scope of the paper to refer to the generality of particular misconceptions across all social and cultural contexts. We hope to spark a debate and further research in this direction.

How do people learn new concepts?

We explored the application of a constructivist approach in education (Piaget, 1953; Vosniadou, 2007; Vygotsky, 1978) to how the personal understanding of biodiversity is formed. In this learning theory, new knowledge builds upon prior knowledge and is constructed through experiences and discoveries, according to a learner's developmental stage (Piaget, 1953). Culture and language play an important role in how this process occurs and its outcome, through limiting the type of experiences that the learners are exposed to and through the impressions that the tutors imprint on the learning process (e.g., values, beliefs) (Vygotsky, 1978). A large body of research by cognitive psychologists and developmental researchers demonstrates that children develop many concepts from their experience of nature (Busch et al., 2018; Waxman & Medin, 2007).

----- Beginning of Box 1

Box 1: What is *biodiversity*?

The definition of biodiversity as the “diversity of living forms” encompasses, perhaps inadvertently, the definition of what diversity in general is. We define the concept of biodiversity for the present perspective in the following way (Figure 1):

- Understanding biodiversity implies understanding the unique aspects of interacting elements, as much as the aspects shared with other elements (their degree of similarity),
- The concept of biodiversity is tightly linked with the concept of inclusion since we can only define a group of elements as diverse, when they are all part of that group.

The degree of similarity between elements of a group depends on the type and number of dimensions in which we choose to describe it. Hence, characterizations of biodiversity will always show a reduced picture of the true diversity in the group. Which dimensions we choose should be done by agreement between all interested parties in describing this biodiversity, with a purposeful aim of doing so and the knowledge that it does not depict the entirety of biodiversity. The number and type of dimensions, the size of the group of inclusion, as well as the position of the elements is for most systems in the world arguable, subjective and can change over time.

Figure 1. Graphical representation of the concept of diversity. The distance between unique elements within a group of inclusion is defined by the degree of similarity along several dimensions, arbitrarily used to characterize them.

----- End of Box 1

A graphical representation of the conceptual model used throughout this perspective about the formation of different personal understandings of knowledge is presented in Figure 2. In this model, knowledge is constructed actively by the learner putting together available pieces of information that are filtered through “invisible membranes” (e.g. cultural biases, social norms) that shape that construction (Roopnarine and Johnson 2015). During the exploration phase, the learner forges a naïve understanding of a topic (Pope and Hilbert 1983, Vosniadou 2007). If contested, further education and experience allow the learner to correct possible misconceptions that may have developed during the exploration phase (this process is known as conceptual change, i.e. note the position of the dark blue tiles – Fig. 2) and to go deeper into a topic, towards an expert understanding (i.e. adding more pieces of knowledge in the correct position to develop a bigger picture of a topic).

Figure 2. A conceptual model of construction of the personal understanding of biodiversity.

The learners get their first notions on a topic (e.g., biodiversity) through exploration of nature and everyday life, shaped by internal and external factors, such as culture. This naïve understanding is later contested and expanded through experience and formal education.

In accordance with this model, there is the possibility that multiple conceptions of biodiversity coexist in society, which we represent by acknowledging both the scientific and social/traditional knowledge conceptions (Figure 3). In Figure 3, the purple circle includes concepts of biodiversity derived by the scientific method. Purple dots within that circle

represent personal understandings of biodiversity. The brown circle denotes social constructs of diversity, which refers to elements in general. The red dots therein represent personal understandings of diversity. The pink circle represents social constructs of biodiversity, which refers to organisms. The understandings of some individuals may have more influence than others; these differences are indicated by circles of different sizes.

Understandings outside the purple circle are misconceptions, at least relative to understandings derived by scientific methods. Such misconceptions may be derived from social explorations. As mentioned earlier, we do not consider social concepts of biodiversity wrong or right on their own; we only consider them to be misunderstandings/misconceptions when they are at odds with a generally accepted conception/understanding in science.

Figure 3.
A

conceptual model of relations between the scientific construct of biodiversity and the social constructs of diversity and biodiversity. The figure shows how, potentially, the social construct of biodiversity is formed in the intersection of the construct of diversity and the scientific concept of biodiversity.

Experiencing biodiversity through puzzles

Games and puzzles are one of the first ways in which many children are introduced to concepts in life (Brown & Freeman, 2001). Through playing and exploring, children instinctively build naïve understandings, based on experience, even without input from formal education. Games, puzzles, books and other media are informal sources of information that encourage interpretations about the biological world, consistent with the beliefs of the mainstream culture (Geerds et al., 2016). Some of these early formed conceptions stick despite formal education and are highly resistant to change (Duit & Treagust, 2003). For example, misunderstandings about natural selection, caused by over-simplification and interpretation of evolution as organisms' "anthropomorphic will to adapt" are widespread in initial education and hard to overcome even after lengthy higher education activities (Emmons et al., 2018; Geerds et al., 2016).

Children’s picture books have been found to influence how children understand the world around them, particularly regarding animals and plants (Ganea et al., 2011; Kelemen et al., 2014). However, less research has been done on the impact of children’s games and puzzles on this understanding. Naïve understandings and conceptual changes (Duit & Treagust, 2003) in sciences have been explored thoroughly for concepts in mathematics, physics, and general biology (e.g. the concept of evolution — but not yet for biodiversity) (Thompson, 2006). We wonder whether such early experiences might have large and long-lasting effects on children’s understandings of biodiversity and its effects on the functioning of ecosystems and the natural world at large (Bermudez and Lindemann-Matthies, 2018).

One puzzle often played by children is known as “Which one does not belong?” It encourages sorting of objects based on differences among them (Figure 4). This puzzle is usually played in its most basic form by young children in kindergarten, often under 6 years old, in relation to mathematics. It is possible that children play the game alone or guided by adult tutors (parents or teachers). The puzzle is common at least in European and North and Latin-American countries, where the authors of this perspective come from, as exemplified by websites such as WODB.ca. Naturally, there are many other puzzles played by children, which would also warrant investigation, but we use this puzzle to illustrate our point and call for further research on this and other games. Furthermore, the diverse situations in which they can be played may influence the conceptions created and influenced by the puzzles.

Figure 4. A typical preschool sorting puzzle, with the title “Watch out! Which one does not belong” representing common descriptions of what such puzzles exclude (“Correct answer”). This image has been based particularly on a game from the brand Bandolino (Germany), which is similar to many others found online in educational websites.

We examined this type of game in particular because the concept of (bio)diversity is clear (there is a group of objects that display some pattern of variation/difference in their properties) and because the player is required to identify a particular element of that diversity

and do something with that pattern of variation. We looked into three aspects of this puzzle and provide possible solutions that can lead to conceptual change: 1) language used, 2) grouping of elements as “correct”, 3) tendency to homogenize (differences between individuals categorized with the same name).

Language used

These puzzles commonly use language that implies difference as an undesirable property of an object, such as “Watch out! Which one does not belong”, “Cross out the picture that does not go with the rest”, “Select the one that does not fit”. We hypothesise that this use of language could lead to a conceptual understanding that difference of one object from others is a negative attribute, and therefore that diversity in a group of objects is undesirable. Hence, from the very earliest age, the language of these puzzles encourages an understanding that being different is a negative attribute, and that different objects when in minority should be excluded from a group. This could be a misconception in general, and certainly is so relative to understandings of the functional importance of biodiversity, in which biodiversity promotes ecosystem functioning and stability (Balvanera et al., 2006; Byrnes et al., 2014; Pennekamp et al., 2018). In such an ecological setting, being different can mean being complementary; things fit and work together often because they are different.

After looking up the educational concept behind “which one does not belong” in websites such as WOBD.ca, we realize that it apparently has the aim to provoke discussion of variety in students’ answers specifically related to math, most clear when using numbers and geometric shapes. In none of the examples using animals or plants there is an intention to discuss biological concepts or an awareness on how this phrasing might be useful in math but harmful in terms of biodiversity understanding.

What changes could be made to these puzzles if they were aimed at creating an experience of differences more likely to result in a positive or neutral (or more complex) attitude towards them (e.g., which one is special/unique)? We hypothesise that simple changes in their titles and descriptions could fundamentally change player’s views of diversity and biodiversity. Moreover, when the children are guided by a tutor, being aware of this misconception as a possible unintended consequence of the game could help them tailor the guidance in order to promote dialogue and clarify whether this is the impression of the student or not. Simply asking questions such as “Have you ever seen these two elements (organisms) together?”, could serve as a starting conversation on when they do belong together and when or why, for practical reasons, we separate them. Alternatively, puzzles could deliberately show groups of elements and ask the child to group the elements that might interact (rather than just to group elements by similarity), thus, for example, a cow would be matched with hay rather than with a pig.

Grouping of elements as “correct”

There are several forms of this puzzle that differ in the number of answers allowed as “correct”. For the ones that allow only one answer, we wonder what sort of impact it could have on the outcomes of the activity for the child, outside mathematics and hard sciences, in particular when elements used are organisms. Furthermore, the reasoning behind the categories promoted can be based on structure or appearance of the elements. Although all of these categories might be useful in different situations, the tutor could be aware of this and in accordance with the level of understanding of the children guide them towards the

most comprehensive picture of the system in consideration. Given that the use of categories to classify objects is one of the educational purposes of these puzzles, we hypothesise that using categories related to more meaningful interactions between the objects in different contexts rather than to their basic shape or colour would serve to achieve a higher understanding of the system, in particular for organisms (such as plants and animals). In contrast, when little interaction between elements is being established, and in the absence of a tutor that invites the child to rethink groups based on different classification schemes, we would risk a limited learning.

Busch et al. (2018) tested children's reasoning when classifying organisms and showed that children naturally favoured ecological reasoning, for example grouping organisms based on their ecological functions (e.g., prey/predator relations) over classification based on taxonomical groups and similarities (Busch et al., 2018). Encouraging classifications that are not based on observable ecological relations between organisms could potentially be a source of misconceptions through the educational process, such as placing all plants as land organisms, or other oversimplifications. What is needed is a change to use interactions between elements which is the fundamental aspect of complementarity, facilitation and division of labour. Multiple answers to puzzles based on different classifications, not necessarily standard across cultures, may help reduce the chances of misconceptions through this game.

Reduced variation and lumping

The last aspect of the puzzles we could look at is the limited variability among objects of the same type; for which the most extreme case would be the example in Figure 4 when the same object is repeated several times with no differences between them. This is especially the case when the objects are organisms. However, this is in stark contrast to the environment around us and in particular the natural world, where variability among elements, even similar ones, is a most general feature. There are hundreds of types of pears (*Pyrus* sp.) known around the world (Bell, 1991), while in these puzzles pears are generally represented in a single way (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Example of different pear varieties, commonly represented by a single type in children's games.

We hypothesise that this over-simplification of organismic diversity could be partially responsible for limited appreciation of biodiversity, due to internal idealizations that homogeneity is normal and perhaps is desirable because there is one "perfect" specimen. The implications of such idealizations without proper intervention from a tutor aware of this issue could be many, from misunderstandings of the concept of biodiversity, to the loss of varieties

and plants and animals, and to the belief that people differ mainly among rather than within certain groups. Interestingly, one can observe such patterns in the real-world production of food. In a nowadays revoked regulation, efforts to standardize food items for the common market of the EU have led to diverging shapes, sizes and colours of vegetables being selected against, masking the true diversity that customers could experience. For example, bananas with an “abnormal curvature” were banned from sale in the EU (European Commission, 1994). Fortunately, this regulation was revoked in 2008, leaving the decision to select to the customers. While such efforts may be well meant in terms of quality control and customer rights, they can lead to detrimental effects. In another example of selection on visual appearance, tomatoes were bred towards an idealized optical phenotype, which has led to a loss of taste through its history of domestication (Tieman et al. 2017). We will expand on how to counter this development in the following section on the value of food diversity to form a deeper understanding of biodiversity.

In science too, underestimating variability within groups, focusing on species levels and removing “outliers”, has been the norm (Des Roches et al., 2018; Violle et al., 2012). Only recently, there is greater recognition and appreciation of the importance of differences among individuals of the same species as the basis of evolution, and that there are advantages gained by viewing diversity at finer scales (Des Roches et al., 2018; Gugerli et al., 2008; Petchey & Gaston, 2002). Thus, it has now been recognized that even at the within-individual level different packaging of chromosomes in cellular nuclei may promote diversity in gene expression within tissues and thus increase organismal functioning (Finn & Misteli 2019).

Many of these games also encourage lumping, by which we mean putting different objects into the same category. Scientists studying biodiversity tend to do a lot of lumping. However, it is becoming clearer that in many situations, lumping creates unjustified, and potentially dangerous perceptions. For example, a study of the potential effects of species extinctions on functional diversity concluded that “75% of the species could be lost before the disappearance of the first functional group” (Fonseca & Ganade, 2001). This percentage is, however, arbitrary due to the subjectivity associated with assigning species to functional groups (Petchey & Gaston, 2002).

While lumping makes the world appear simpler and apparently more understandable, it can have negative consequences such as being unwillingly subjected to biased classifications made by others (biased to a political view, for example), slowing progress (there is an inertia to change classifications that are established in a system) or limiting our creativity (Bowker & Leigh Star, 1999). The sense of safety from reducing the complexities comes with an unrealistic view of the world (Voinov et al., 2014). We hypothesize that research into this compression of diversity into categories/groups/tribes of seemingly identical objects will reveal that it is generally unnecessary and undesirable.

Experiencing biodiversity through food-related activities

A common and particularly intimate experience of biodiversity comes through what we eat. Eating is an important connection with nature, from which we obtain energy and a diversity of nutrients for our existence. There are indications that children establish priorities in biodiversity conservation based on the type of biodiversity to which they are exposed (Ballouard et al., 2011). There is a rich corpus of research on the importance of dietary diversity (Kant et al., 1993; Taruvinga et al., 2013) and numerous studies that link biodiversity education and conservation to different aspects of nutrition (Chipeniuk, 1995; Crist, Mora, & Engelman, 2017; Fischer et al., 2019). Research shows that getting involved with the local

plants and animals has a positive influence in children's environmental attitudes and potentially helps them become better at making decisions regarding environmental management (Brewer, 2002). Even when those responses are not beneficial *per se* towards conservation, exposure to biodiversity helped students make wiser decisions, for example, differentiating toxic and nontoxic plants (Prokop & Fančovičová, 2019).

We therefore suggest that analogies between cooking/eating and biodiversity theory could be used much more in education about biodiversity. Furthermore, we hypothesise that there is considerable potential to make the biodiversity present more visible. Given the wide variety of food traditions across cultures, this approach could be at the same time useful to do research in comparing how different societies relate to the diversity in their diets, possibly having an influence in the way they understand and form attitudes towards biodiversity.

Cooking and biodiversity science analogies

Food fills the senses with a variety of colours, smells and textures; features derived from the intrinsic diversity of traits in the organisms humans consume. Recipes are combinations of parts of different organisms that interact creating new elements of different value; a concrete analogy to the importance of species composition/combinations for phenomena such as ecological coexistence and stability (de Mazancourt et al., 2013; Loreau & de Mazancourt, 2013). Because the food prepared following recipes is more than the sum of its parts, putting a value on the contributions of each individual ingredient is difficult; this is analogous to the difficulties in isolating individual species contributions to ecosystem functioning (Lawton & Brown, 1994). For many recipes, diversity is a necessary requirement, but appropriate combinations and inclusion methods are also necessary. This is echoed in many biodiversity–ecosystem functioning experiments, in which diversity and composition are simultaneously important determinants of ecosystem functioning (Spehn et al., 2005; Hector et al., 2001). Finally, more diverse ingredients do not necessarily make a better final dish, the same as more biodiversity is not, *per se*, always better for an ecosystem to function or ecosystem service to work. We hypothesise that these parallels between food/cooking and biodiversity can be employed in education about biodiversity, as they can be derived from an everyday activity, such as obtaining ingredients or even gathering wild foods or growing food in a garden and cooking them (Poe et al. 2013). As with the example of the games, to ensure a deep and correct understanding of biodiversity using these analogies, they should be employed by a tutor, teacher or guidance of sort, guiding the students to develop the parallels themselves.

Tracking biodiversity in diet

The diversity in the food people eat could have implications beyond nutrition; it could be one of the few access points to nature they have in everyday life and therefore silently influence the way they understand biodiversity. We hypothesise that the lack of connection between the biological diversity in our diets and the natural world partially explains difficulties in understanding the concept of biodiversity. If people are not familiar with food diversity, it is possible that they will not understand how to protect its sources.

In most of the developed world, the trend is for most people to be detached from the resources they consume. For examples, one of us was not aware as a child that Sauerkraut was made from cabbage and as the teacher asked this question to the class, most of the children between 7–9 years of age did not know it either; this was 60 years ago in a small town in Switzerland (Bernhard Schmid, personal recollection). There may be few

environmental sustainability considerations when people choose their diets and there is a dietary delocalization, which is proven to be both environmentally damaging and unhealthy (Rose et al., 2019; van der Horst et al., 2011). Yet, it seems that many people yearn for contact with nature (Clark et al., 2019). At the same time many species of crops, vegetables and fruits are underused in global diets, and within the ones being used the same occurs to varieties (FAO et al., 2017). While the relation between agricultural diversity and human nutrition has been somewhat explored, less importance has been given to developing concrete tools for people to track diversity in their own diets (Johns et al., 2013; Toledo & Burlingame, 2006). Providing tools to this end would help to raise awareness on the level of diversity we foster and consume and the general sustainability of our diets.

How can students learn about biodiversity by paying attention to their experiences of diversity through food, and increase the visibility of biodiversity in their daily life? Here we developed a table with the criteria that we considered relevant, so that it could be used independently or by educators, to strengthen people’s connection with the biodiversity in their diet (Figure 6). Ideally, such a table would be adapted to the local context and accompanied with a) information on how to fill in the columns, b) nutritional information for a healthy diet and c) crop, fruit and vegetable calendars with information on the availability of diverse food sources including species and varieties that could be used to reach the healthy diet.

With respect to the third point (availability of diverse food sources) a complementary activity to encourage is the setting of local community gardens, for exchange of information and for locally sourced food. Given that not everyone has access to land or resources to have their own garden, we think more nation-wide programmes should be fostered and encouraged. Participating in school gardens, for example, has been shown to increase understanding of biodiversity in children that were involved in gardening activities (Fischer et al., 2019; Guitart et al., 2014).

Complete the table with information about the food you had in the last week				
Food name (product)	<i>Beef</i>	<i>Corn</i>	<i>Cheese</i>	<i>Ginger</i>
Common name of organism	<i>Cow</i>	<i>Maize</i>	<i>Cow</i>	<i>Ginger</i>
Kingdom	<i>Animalia</i>	<i>Plantae</i>	<i>Animalia</i>	<i>Plantae</i>
Phylum/Division	<i>Chordata</i>	<i>Tracheophyta</i>	<i>Chordata</i>	<i>Tracheophyta</i>
Species (Latin name)	<i>Bos taurus</i>	<i>Zea mays</i>	<i>Bos taurus</i>	<i>Zingiber officinale</i>
Whole, part or derivated?	<i>part</i>	<i>part</i>	<i>derivate</i>	<i>part</i>
Name of part or part where it derivates from	<i>flesh</i>	<i>seed</i>	<i>milk</i>	<i>root</i>
Number of times consumed (e.g., per week)	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>1</i>
Country where it comes from	<i>Switzerland</i>	<i>unknown</i>	<i>Switzerland</i>	<i>India</i>
Distance it travelled to your place (km)	<i>100</i>	<i>---</i>	<i>300</i>	<i>7000</i>

Figure 6. Example of a table that could help us analyse the biodiversity in our diets (Biodiversity and Global Change MOOC, University of Zurich).

A call for more interdisciplinary research into how biodiversity understanding is shaped

Here we have presented our ideas and perspective on how everyday experiences and practices could inadvertently shape personal understandings of biodiversity and provided numerous hypotheses that could be tested. A general suggestion is that researchers should scrutinize representations of biodiversity and research how learners respond to these. Further, work on these representations, which are not strictly part of environmental education or ethnobotany work or about the psychology of learning, could nevertheless warrant consideration in all these areas. Also, any arising research should consider relevant work from the field of cognitive psychology (e.g. about categories and concepts) that would situate research within a larger corpus of literature (e.g., Margolis & Laurence, 2015; Murphy, 2002).

We propose that research on how people develop biodiversity understandings consider experiences outside formal science education. A concrete implementation for the games is to foster collaboration among different disciplines in game design and when possible to test the outcome of the impact that they have in understanding, e.g., through interventions, experiments or surveys. A concrete implementation for food-related activities would be to develop and provide more resources for tracking biodiversity in our own diets. More broadly, we support policies that increase access to direct experiences of biodiversity, such as those that foster agro-biodiversity and counteract the worldwide loss of varieties via re-engagement with diverse food systems.

For example, we proposed that during the development of educational games that use organisms as elements, potentially negative consequences about the understanding of and attitudes towards biodiversity should be considered. Moreover, a game aimed to educate or practice concepts of mathematics could potentially have negative consequences in biodiversity understanding, if not carefully phrased and framed by a tutor. The reasoning behind classifying and sorting games is the development of goal-oriented behaviours (executive functions), such as working memory or mental flexibility and learning-related cognitive skills, such as math or reading (Ackerman & Friedman-Krauss, 2017). We do not question the relevance of developing these skills, but we want to raise the hypothesis that such games may have unintended and potentially undesirable effects on how children playing them understand biodiversity. It seems worth further exploring the effects that these games have on understandings of biodiversity. For example when these early learning exercises are complemented by others from environmental education settings, perhaps more positive connotations of diversity will be fostered and children might develop a conceptual change from oversimplistic representations to a more nuanced, multifaceted conception of biodiversity (e.g., Figure 7). We acknowledge that the example in figure 6 is more sophisticated and cognitively demanding than the originals in figure 4, hence suited for older children. It is difficult to avoid oversimplifications of biodiversity in pursuit of making a question/puzzle developmentally appropriate for small children. To understand the impact of games on the children that play them, collaborations between biodiversity scientists, education experts and game designers need to be developed and strengthened.

Figure 7: Goal-oriented alternative puzzles with multiple answers (similar to what could be found in the field of environmental education) in which diversity is acknowledged and can be perceived as positive or neutral attributes of a system.

Furthermore, we encourage more studies on the relationship between food experiences and people’s understanding of biodiversity, as we believe they have great potential to sow the seeds for dialogue (Barthel et al., 2013). Our diets are strongly connected with culture and with agricultural diversity. By highlighting the role of biodiversity in something as tangible as food, we suggest that people’s general connection with nature would be enhanced and most likely also the understanding of it.

We emphasize that the concept represented in the sorting game discussed above—that structural differences make an element not “fit” to be part of a group—can be a misconception when taken in isolation, without qualification, context, or nuance, especially when referring to biodiversity. We ask if such misconceptions lead to an under-appreciation of the role of biodiversity by implying that parts of a groups should be the same and thus biodiversity is not important. Such misconceptions could be problematic if they hinder the capacity to comprehend the role of biodiversity in ecological functions. While we discuss understanding the function of diversity of species and choosing a diverse diet, other areas of inquiry could include cultural expressions (television, theatre), transport, and landscape or city design. These issues at the same time help shape people’s view of the world and are forms of expression. In these areas we can explore representations of the diversity of elements, ideas and resources. Highlighting the role of biodiversity in relation with these everyday topics would likely help us discover what other experiences shape understanding, and when and for whom.

There are possible caveats and limitations to our (the authors’) perspective. Primarily, as mentioned above, we are naturally limited to our own experiences from our countries of origin and socio-economic situations. We wish to avoid generalizing ideas or implying that everyone has similar experiences with the kinds of puzzles and games describe, or access to diverse diets or information on food nutrition. We are aware that many people, even in developed countries, do not have access to such resources and that in many cultures these ideas may not apply. It would be interesting to have an inter-cultural and inclusive discussion

about which other forms of biodiversity representations could be influencing the understanding of biodiversity for people not contemplated in this article.

Secondarily, it is important to note that we do not think that all experiences of biodiversity should be orchestrated to create only positive attitudes towards it. It is easy to find genuine experiences of biodiversity that lead to positive attitudes (e.g., aesthetic value of diverse pastures), or to negative attitudes (e.g., human wildlife conflicts for land resources) (Schneegg & Kiaka, 2018). However, alignment of people's understandings with well-evidenced and broadly accepted scientific conclusions, e.g. that more often than not biodiversity loss has negative consequences for ecosystems, will likely require that educators attend to everyday experiences that might shape how biodiversity is understood.

Lastly, by investigating the view of biodiversity created through everyday life, it is possible that we direct the focus to local biodiversity, rather than a global or distant one. The intention would be to increase the quality of connections between people and nature by removing misconceptions. This could lead to wider support for conservation. However, a general understanding of global issues such as declines in biodiversity due to climate change or impact of global trade on the environment would still require additional efforts in education that certainly exceed what one can live through daily experiences.

Declaration of interests

The authors declare no competing interests in the writing of this manuscript.

Author's contributions and disclosure statement

M.A.P. performed the literature research, developed first draft of models, wrote first complete draft of manuscript and coordinated co-authors contributions. S.P. and M.C. participated in the development of the educational framework on personal and social understanding of biodiversity. F.A., N.B., A.D.-Z., K.H., P.N., M.M., F.P., M.J.S., M.S., B.S., V.W.M. and D.Z.-D. contributed to overall manuscript writing and provided references for specific sections and topics. I.R.G. participated in the development of the figures. O.L.P. initiated the idea of the manuscript, wrote initial summary and first draft of key sections of the manuscript, invited co-authors and supervised the development of manuscript. None of the co-authors has any interests to declare.

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